

XRD

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Standard Operating Procedure

Title: Powder X-ray diffraction measurements for nanoparticles

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1. Scope and application

The scope of this SOP is to provide a description of the methodology to be used for the application of powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) to the analysis of nanoparticles both in powder and suspension form.

XRD will provide:

- 1) The crystalline phase composition of the material
- 2) The average size of the crystalline domains (or crystallite size)
- 3) The presence of an amorphous phase

This SOP has been applied to several type of nanoparticles amongst which, SiO₂, TiO₂, CeO₂.

2. Terms, definitions and normative references

The normative references are reported in the chapter 11, whilst the abbreviation are defined in chapter 3.

3. Abbreviated terms

FWHM: Full Width Half Maximum

FoM: Figure-of-Merit

ICDD: International Centre of Diffraction Data

IPD: Individual Protective Devices

PDF: Powder Diffraction File

XRD: X-ray diffraction

4. Method principle

XRD is a common and rapid characterization technique for nanoscale materials, primarily used for crystalline phase identification and crystallite size. The components of commercial XRD instruments - an X-ray source, a sample holder and an X-ray detector - are mounted on a goniometer that is able to move their position at various angles with respect to the horizontal plane. In a typical XRD measurement, monochromatic X-rays are directed into the sample, and the intensity of the reflected X-rays is recorded as the source and/or the detector are rotated. When the geometry of the incident X-rays hitting the sample satisfies the Bragg Equation, constructive interference occurs, thereby causing a peak in intensity. As the position of diffracted peaks in an XRD spectrum depends on the geometry of the unit cell, crystalline phase identification is possible by comparing the XRD patterns with spectra hosted in existing datasets (e.g. ICDD PDF). Moreover, XRD results can provide other important information, such as the average size of crystalline domains and the degree of crystallinity.

5. Safety procedures and precautions

See chapter 6.

6. Procedure

The goal of this section is to identify all relevant steps and the resources needed to accomplish the procedures, such as method calibration, sample preparation and analysis, data acquisition, etc.

6.1 Apparatus and equipment

List of items required

- Sample holder with shallow well (e.g. PMMA specimen holder from supplier)
- Airtight specimen holder equipped with a beryllium dome – specific for powders that pose a health hazard if inhaled (e.g. multi-walled carbon nanotubes).
- Mortar and pestle
- Fume hood for hazardous materials
- Drying device: desiccator, oven or chamber under vacuum
- Flat supports (area $\approx 1 \times 1$ cm): amorphous support, such as glass slide, or crystalline support, such as Si wafer. The choice of the support depends on the deposited material.
- Micropipettes and tips
- Device for material deposition, such as chamber under vacuum or spin-coater (such as Apogee™ Spin Coater)
- Powder-free and Si-free gloves
- Powder mask
- Protective goggles
- Acquisition and analysis software package: e.g. DIFFRAC.SUITE (Bruker) for data acquisition and OriginPro 2015 (OriginLab) for data analysis
- X-ray diffractometer, e.g. Bruker D8 Discovery diffractometer

6.2 Chemicals, reference materials and reagents

The following chemicals, materials and reagents are required

- Acetone (CH₃)₂CO CAS 67-64-1
- Ethanol CH₃CH₂OH CAS 64-17-5

-Hexane CH₃(CH₂)₄CH₃ CAS 110-54-3

-Sample storage:

-Powders should be stored in sealed glass bottles, possibly in dark, room temperature and low humidity conditions (if not otherwise specified)

Use of individual protection devices (IPD) equipment is required

6.3 Samples

Samples to be analysed could be in dry form or in suspension. The amounts usually needed for the analysis are:

- Dry nanoparticles: 0.5-1.0 g depending on material type
- Suspensions: 0.1 -5.0 mL depending on concentration

6.4 Performing measurements

6.4.1 Sample preparation

Dry nanoparticles (powders)

- Weigh ca. 0.5-1.0 g of material and keep it at 80°C overnight to remove adsorbed water. Alternatively, a desiccator can be used. The amount of material weighed here should be enough to fill up the well of the XRD specimen holder.

- Crush the material (e.g. with a pestle in a mortar) to reduce grain size. Grinding should be performed with a mild force to avoid too small particles or lattice damage. After that, store the powder under vacuum or in a desiccator.

-Deposit the powder in the shallow well of the XRD specimen holder. Use a slightly rough flat surface (such as a glass slide) to press down the powder, packing it into the well.

For materials which pose a health hazard if inhaled, place the powder directly into an airtight specimen holder equipped with a beryllium window.

Suspensions

If the material is not sufficient for filling up a specimen holder with a shallow well, it can be suspended in a suitable solvent (acetone, ethanol, water, etc.) and then deposited as thin films on flat supports. To this end, any technique yielding thin deposited layers can be used. This protocol focuses on spin coating and drop casting, which can be alternatively used depending on the available volume of dispersions.

a. Spin coating. Large volumes (even up to 5 mL) are required because several material-wasting spinning steps are needed. Use the stock suspension as received or dilute it to have a larger volume.

-Place the flat support on the chuck of the spin coater and cover it completely with the suspension (usually 50-150 μ l are sufficient).

-Start spinning to achieve solvent evaporation (for example with the following parameters: spin speed > 1500 rpm, speed ramp > 1000 rpm/s)

-Repeat the whole process until the desired thickness is achieved. The required thickness is sample-dependent, as it strongly depends on the material's linear adsorption coefficient.

b. Drop casting. As this technique does not waste material, it is suitable for small volumes. In this case, the concentration of the suspension should be low enough to ensure both a good attachment to the support and a uniform distribution of the material. Therefore, sample preparation might require some time to find the correct concentration.

- Cast a 10 μ l droplet of the suspension onto the flat support

- Dry it under vacuum or by using a desiccator.

-Repeat the procedure until the desired thickness.

6.4.2 Measurement description

Sample mounting

For dry nanoparticles, the filled specimen holder should be placed on the sample stage at the centre of the goniometer of the diffractometer.

For suspensions, the coated flat support should be first fixed at the centre of a sample holder and then placed on the sample stage.

Instrument settings

Settings are chosen on a case-by-case basis depending on the sample type and crystallinity. Generally speaking, selected settings should lead to the acquisition of at least 7 points above the half-maximum of each diffraction peak and to a signal/noise ratio that proves sufficient for a good peak fitting (i.e. fitting with adjusted $R^2 > 0.98$). An example of instrument settings is the following:

X-ray tube: Cu anode ($\lambda_{K\alpha} = 0.15406$ nm), voltage: 40 kV, current: 40 mA.

Incident beam optics: Göbel's mirror, divergence slit 0.6 mm, Soller slit 2.5°

Diffracted beam optics: divergence slit 0.6 mm, Soller slit 2.5°

Detector: 0D Lynxeye - Detector Energy resolution <680 eV at 8 keV (Cu radiation) at 298K

Measurement settings

Measurement settings are chosen on a case-by-case basis depending on the sample type and crystallinity. For example, a materials deposited as thin film will usually require more acquisition time than the same material deposited in a powder well to get the same peak intensity in the diffractogram. An example of measurement settings is the following:

Geometry: Bragg-Brentano (coupled $\theta/2\theta$) is a geometry that is commonly used to obtain qualitative information from XRD measurements. If peaks that are deemed important appear at $2\theta < 15^\circ$, the grazing angle (2θ) geometry should be used, fixing the angular position of the source ($\theta=3-6$ degrees).

2θ range = usually between 15 and 80 degrees

2θ step = 0.01 – 0.05 degrees

2θ scan speed = 2-10 s per step

Rotation (only for coupled $\theta/2\theta$ geometry) = 60 rpm

6.4.3 Data Analysis

The diffractometer's manufacturer usually makes a dedicated evaluation software available. For Bruker D8 Discovery, the evaluation software DIFFRAC SUITE EVA can be used to determine the material's crystalline phase(s). For calculation of crystallite size, data should be exported to a data analysis software that enables peak fitting and integration (such as OriginPro 2015 from OriginLab).

1. *Crystal phase composition.* The material crystal phase(s) can be identified by matching the recorded diffractograms with existing files stored in a powder diffraction file library (such as ICDD PDF-2016). A good match is described by a FoM between 80 and 150 .
2. *Crystallite size.* After exporting diffractograms to a data analysis software, each peak's position and FWHM should be obtained by fitting via suitable line shapes (such as pseudo-Voigt function). Peak position and FWHM can be used to calculate the average crystallite size via the Scherrer equation.
3. *Presence of amorphous phase.* Broad and large peaks whose line-shape can be better fitted by a Gaussian than by a pseudo-Voigt function are very often evidence of the presence of amorphous phase. Evaluation software tools such as DIFFRAC.SUITE.EVA can usually perform a rough estimation of the degree of amorphousness by dividing the peak area belonging to amorphous and crystalline phase.

7. Quality control

A standard quality control can be done by analysing instrument response (line positions, intensities and 2θ scale) by measuring the standard reference sample SRM 1976c (corundum disk) and comparing the results with the control measurement done after calibration by the Bruker technician (at installation and/or maintenance).

8. Measurement uncertainty and traceability

Phase identification. Many sources of error are associated with the Bragg-Brentano geometry (Sample Displacement Error Sample, Axial divergence etc.) which can cause peak shift or asymmetric broadening effects. Such effects can lead to a poor matching when identifying crystalline phase via a PDF library.

Crystallite size. The Scherrer equation is understood to give a very rough estimation of the crystallite size and strongly depends on the value of Scherrer constant chosen (which can range between 0,8 to about 1,4).

Other common source of instrumental error are:

Sample height displacement, Sample surface is located too low / high with respect to the goniometer physical center (which causes focus of diffracted beam being displaced, receiving slit / 1D / 2D detector out of focus, diffracted beam blocked by optical elements and results in 2θ shift of peaks, diffuse / broad peaks, loss of intensity, anomalous peak profiles).

Rough sample surface (which causes diffraction signals from different surface levels, focus of diffracted beam is partially displaced, receiving slit / 1D / 2D detector out of focus and results in 2θ shift of peaks, Diffuse / broad peaks, anomalous peak profiles)

Sample transparency, deep penetration of radiation into the sample (which causes diffraction signals from different surface levels, focus of diffracted beam is partially displaced, receiving slit / 1D / 2D detector out of focus and results in 2θ shift of peaks, diffuse / broad peaks, anomalies in peak profiles)

During powder samples preparation for Bragg-Brentano geometry measurements care should be taken in order to have:

1. Crystallites and particles of 1-5 μm size
2. Perfectly random orientation
3. Perfectly flat surface
4. Surface precisely centred in the goniometer
5. Short penetration depth

9. Reporting of results

The results obtained could be reported in Excel (2016) or Origin (OriginPro 2015) table, whilst fitted spectra can be exported as txt files for plotting or saved as images in bmp or jpg format.

10. Validation status

in house

ILC

11. Literature references

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12. Document approval

Approval by:

Date	Name	Job title	Signature